

Book Reviews

Rebuilding Britain: Planning for a Better Future, Hugh Ellis and Kate Henderson, *Bristol, Policy Press*, 2014, 120 pp., £14.99, ISBN: 978-1-4473-17593

Contemporary Britain is beset by crisis: from housing and demographic crises, to the urban and global financial crisis, to perhaps *the* biggest crisis of all, looming catastrophic climate change – all seemingly rendered impossible to resolve by a crisis in democratic decision-making. This short, readable and passionately argued book punches well above its weight in attempting to address these 21st century challenges head on. Hugh Ellis and Kate Henderson identify the central problem as one of a failure of national and regional planning for the future. Inspired by the early town planning tradition, notably the Garden City movement, they point to the forgotten art of utopian thinking and call on the British planning system to reinvent itself as a renewed force for progressive social change.

The book is written in an engaging and informative style that treads carefully between well-referenced academic textbook, pragmatic policy prescription and unabashedly political polemic. Ellis and Henderson break their argument down into four easily digestible parts: first laying out their vision for reengaging planning in utopian thinking, introducing the history of the early town planning movement and its co-evolution with anarchist and utopian ideas; second, making the empirical case for why we need to think big again, with subchapters on social, economic, political and environmental crises; third, suggesting practical solutions borrowed from utopian history and contemporary exemplars in sustainable urbanism, such as Freiburg and Malmo; before finally bringing the argument full circle by considering the contradictions and potential of realising utopia.

Common ownership and democratic

control of land is presented as the key to unlocking the potential of planning, in a section entitled ‘the lie of the land!’ The authors argue that land ownership is the elephant in the room: the foundation of all wealth creation and *the* scarce resource, concentrated so unequally in the hands of neo-feudal landowners. Drawing on pragmatic utopian experiments in land reform from British history, notably the Garden City movement, the authors argue for a new system of cooperative ownership and land value capture in urban development, whereby all surpluses, the ‘unearned increment’, are recycled back into the local area for community benefit rather than siphoned off by absentee landlords as profit. This comes as no surprise: Ellis and Henderson are the current head of policy and chief executive, respectively, of the Town and Country Planning Association (TCPA), the modern heir of Ebenezer Howard’s Garden Cities Association.

Achieving such a vision is problematic in our so-called post-political or post-democratic society, in which public services have been privatised and outsourced and our planning system transformed into an unaccountable, narrowly technocratic enterprise concerned above all with economic growth and efficiency (Allmendinger and Haughton, 2012). A particularly shocking consequence revealed in the book is that Britain is the only country in northwest Europe that lacks a national plan or even a regional planning framework, which are convincingly argued as essential prerequisites for tackling the huge multi-scalar challenges of national infrastructure redevelopment, regional socioeconomic redistribution and climate change adaptation.

Despite the obvious ideological and institutional challenges to the practical uptake of their ideas, Ellis and Henderson make an impassioned plea for rediscovering the lost art

of planning as a future-oriented purposive activity with political *vision*. Cutting through these utopian ambitions is a tension between temporal process and spatial form, procedure and end state – which can also be seen in planning theory: in the shift from modernist technocratic blueprint plan-making towards a postmodern concern with mediating partnerships, consulting stakeholders and facilitating collaborative planning *processes*. We have seen a concomitant shift from *spatial* utopias – the kind of ideal cities envisioned by Ebenezer Howard and Le Corbusier – towards *temporal* utopias, the techno-optimism of free-flowing global digital networks. Likewise, a similar tension in utopian-socialist thought (Harvey, 2000) balances the need to construct a definite space for new ways of life to emerge against the tendency of spatial closure to constrain experimental open-ended change.

Ellis and Henderson acknowledge that ‘we also need to consider a new way of living and organising ourselves which values cooperation as much as we currently value competition’ (81). But the brevity and format of the book prevents a deeper engagement with these issues, and perhaps shows a bias towards reforming the legal and political structures of planning over its everyday social practices. It is surprising to find no reference to the late Colin Ward, the anarchist planning writer, whose pragmatic anarchism celebrated the ‘seeds beneath the snow’ – those do-it-yourself self-help experiments in cooperative living and mutual aid rooted in practical everyday life, which, if carefully cultivated and given the space to grow, could eventually transform the state incrementally from within. Progress with such grassroots experimentation can be seen, for example, in the 1970s housing cooperative movement in Liverpool, inspired by Ward’s (1974) ideas for collective dweller control; and Liverpool’s contemporary urban community land trust

movement, emerging in the same inner-city neighbourhoods (Thompson, in press). The challenge is how to gear the planning system towards enabling more social innovation like this.

Like Colin Ward, Ellis and Henderson take inspiration from the anarchist ‘early pioneers like Kropotkin and Carpenter [who] saw people taking their own decisions to the point where the national state became insignificant’; but nonetheless acknowledge that ‘we appear to be a long way away from that point’ (94). Rebuilding Britain is riven by the central tension of reconciling moves towards a decentralised, participatory and locally-responsive decision-making process with the urgent socioecological need to achieve large-scale societal transformation seeming to require centrally-directed, expert-led strategic planning. These difficult questions are dealt with brilliantly in Andrew Cumbers’ (2012) recent book on reclaiming economic democracy through decentralised common ownership, citing Danish wind farm co-ops as innovative ways to achieve local control of complex infrastructure; resonating with similar examples provided in *Rebuilding Britain*, such as the pioneering re-municipalisation of Hamburg’s energy grid.

In dealing with such all-encompassing subject matter, some might accuse Ellis and Henderson of carving out too expansive a role for planning beyond its traditional land regulation scope. However, their admirable utopian ambitions make for a refreshing read for all implicated in the fate of planning, and I hope this book will be read by policy-makers, practitioners, researchers, teachers, and students alike. Ellis and Henderson are unafraid to resurrect the difficult and unfashionable concept of utopia, despite its many contradictions, not least the ever-present danger of dystopia: ‘the utopian tradition has always run the risk of creating

monolithic places which at their very worst can be oppressive and very often just plain boring' (141). In closing, they paint an impression of their envisioned utopia, and assure us that 'there will be space for art and space for creative chaos' (140). The question remains, however, whether creativity and spontaneity can **ever be** *designed in to space?*

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Land Policy: Planning and the Spatial Consequences of Property, Benjamin Davy, *Farnham, Ashgate*, 2012, 292 pp., £65.00, ISBN 978-0-7546-7792-5

Most planners will agree that land is a key subject for our discipline and that decisions about property rights for using land are important for many aspects of planning practice. But publications about land policy offering a fresh theoretical perspective are rare. So when this book was announced, I was curious to see how Benjamin Davy would approach this theme.

Interested readers should be in no doubt – this is a theoretical book, crossing disciplinary boundaries of economics, law, cultural studies and planning. Chapter 1 provides a brief introduction to planning and three so-called myths of property: Control, liberty and similarity, each referring to key authors associated with those concepts, namely Thomas Hobbes, John Locke and Jean-Jacques Rousseau. This is followed by two examples of large-scale urban renewal

projects, Lake Phoenix in Germany and Sabarmati Riverfront in India. Chapter 2 focuses on the spatial theory of land rent and discusses problems associated with applying such a mono-rational theory in policymaking. Following this, chapter 3 introduces polyrationality – discussing in particular different notions of property and how one can use Mary Douglas' grid-group theory to define eight mono-rational types of land uses. Chapter 4 turns towards the issue of land value, arguing that land policy can be interpreted as value management, differentiating between exchange value, use value, territorial value and existence value. Chapters 5 and 6 provide a review of property in land, particularly focussing on the differentiation between private and common property, while also discussing the human right aspects of access to property, and politics of belonging. Chapters 7 and 8 bring together the key arguments of the book, outlining a concept for polyrational policymaking and how this can be used within planning.

The preface explains the author's

motivations for writing the book. Davy aims to look beyond the Western concepts of ownership by referring to experiences from the Global South while also considering the human rights aspects of property. Furthermore he hopes that the international debate about land policy can benefit from an insight into spatial planning, property and land policy in Germany. But readers expecting an in-depth analysis of planning and land policy in Germany may be disappointed, as the main focus of the book is discussing and conceptualising polyrational land policy, arguing that a monorational approach often leads to policy failure. Still, within this thematic context some aspects of German land policy are used as examples throughout the book. This includes specific policy tools like mandatory land readjustment and statutory real estate appraisal, a brief overview of regulatory planning, and more recent developments like the land thrift policy with its 30ha/day target for new urbanisation until 2020. Beyond this there are also references to the historic context of German planning and land policy including the Nazi Lebensraum concept and the way the post-war constitutional and legal system in Germany has tried to find a balance between private and common property interests.

Despite taking a predominantly theoretical perspective, Davy aims to provide some useful advice for planning practice. This includes simple statements repeated throughout the book such as land uses are what land users do' or 'Good land policy provides a diversity of land uses with plural property relations'. Furthermore the two cases of large scale urban regeneration projects in Germany and India introduced in chapter 1 are used throughout the book as examples, though to really appreciate these examples, providing more information about the general context of planning and

regeneration in Germany and India would have been useful. The typology of 8 rationalities of property developed throughout the book is meant as a guideline for planners to help them navigate the polyrationality of land property in planning practice. As the author admits at various points in the book, some planners already practice what the book argues for, a polyrational approach. But given the focus on polyrational land policy and planning, I was surprised to find only a few reflections on the role of the planner and the different forms of planning processes throughout the book. It would have been interesting to discuss how different approaches which have been discussed and developed within planning theory over recent decades relate to the polyrational approach towards land policy proposed in the book. This includes debates about advocacy, mediation, participation or collaborative planning, as all of these approaches aim to consider different perspectives or rationalities within a planning process.

One of the more interesting aspects of the book is the in-depth discussion of the historic origins of property philosophies, going back to the 17th century. Davy also introduces readers to lesser known concepts and thinkers such as the Policy-Wissenschaft work of Heinrich Gottlob von Justi, which was an early precursor of political economy, arguing that efficient and useful land use should be a goal for governments. In particular the chapters discussing land rent, land values, ownership and belonging would be a great study text on the respective subjects for students, as the text contains many direct quotes and cross-references while also repeating key points and arguments from previous chapters. While this style of writing is an advantage if used as a text book just reading individual chapters, the repetition of key arguments gets tiring when

reading the book from beginning to end, as core arguments and key references recur throughout the book. Some of the chapters and sub-chapters have rather cryptic titles including ‘Unhappy boundaries’, ‘Umbaga – the second spear’ or ‘She told ya fun names!’. While such language might evoke amusement and curiosity amongst some readers, it does not help communicate the logic of the argument and the structure of the book. Furthermore the eight chapters would have benefitted from introduction and summary

paragraphs at the beginning and end of each chapter, and a general introduction outlining the structure of the book at the start of chapter 1. Overall this book is a welcome addition to the literature on land policy providing a fresh cross-disciplinary perspective beyond the usual focus on land economics or statutory land use planning.

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The Social Atlas of Europe, Dimitris Ballas, Danny Dorling and Benjamin Hennig, *London, Policy Press*, 2014, 311 pp., £24.99, ISBN 978-1-44731-353-3

The Social Atlas of Europe highlights the notion that Europe as a continent, and as a group of countries can be conceived as a single entity. Through the innovative use of geographic information system (GIS) [AQ1] and cartographic techniques the authors display the multiple human geographies of Europe, highlighting that Europe is not simply a collection of nation states, but an amalgamation of multiple regions which are both heterogeneous but also share many commonalities – revealing multiple different views of Europe. The authors, three geographers, attempt to display the realities of Europe from the perspective of human geography, developing a sense of the national, regional and spatial differences across the continent. *The Social Atlas of Europe* uses GIS and cartographic techniques to offer alternative views of Europe, focusing less on national boundaries as they rarely reflect the social and economic realities, but more on characteristics of the people and places within the continent.

The book contains maps or cartograms,

divided into categories addressing different elements of European society including: identity and culture; demographics, education; employment; industry and occupation; health; politics; economics; environment; social cohesion and policy. Questions addressed in the atlas range from the consideration of the percentage of people in Europe who believe in life after death, how important politics is in an individual’s life, to explorations of GDP or foreign direct investment; to net payments into the EU budget. Given that the exploration of population characteristics and how they change are central to the work of planners – whether this be to cope with growth (Churski and Dominiak, 2014), shrinkage (Sousa and Pinho, 2015) or transformation (Therkildsen et al., 2009), these visualisations should serve as key points to inform discussions within the planning discipline.

There are three key types of visualisations included in the book – country cartograms, cartograms with thematic mapping, and gridded population Hennig cartograms. The first type uses a rainbow colour scheme showing countries resized according to their population, the second type uses shaded cartograms to show distribution of the population feature in discussion, and the

third uses gridded population cartograms, where the size of each grid cell reflects the number of people living in the area, using finer level geographical information about the populations in question than the previous two types. These are different to traditional maps as they are shaped to be proportional in accordance with the social statistics rather than just their physical features. In these maps, population is the key variable.

It would be impossible in a review of this length to do justice to the range of visualisations presented in this volume, and so those mentioned here are simply illustrative of the contributions. While the number of unemployed people is frequently discussed in policy discussions and the media, the visual representation included in the atlas shows the huge variety which exists in the content, with Spain clearly dominating the landscape (nearly 4 million unemployed in 2012). Similarly the map which shows the increase in unemployed people between 2007 and 2013 highlights the spatially variegated nature of the impacts of the financial crisis. Conversely when you observe the decline in unemployment between 2007 and 2012 the map is hardly recognisable as Europe as Germany dominates the picture. While many of the issues covered in the book are likely to be at the fore of political discussions, it also includes more novel cartograms which would not necessarily make their way into publications – one of these is the total votes received in the 2013 European song contest and the total votes given to the UK – revealing a lot about the politics of Europe.

It is clear that the authors have made an effort to use the most recent data where it is available, although it is inevitable that with representations of populations which are by nature dynamic and ever-changing that they will become somewhat outdated. For example, where net adjusted income of private households for 2007 is displayed,

the pattern is likely to have been affected by the 2008 financial crisis, and therefore it would be interesting to see how much this pattern has changed. This issue of keeping data and visualisations current is somewhat counteracted by new maps published on the dedicated Europemapper website which accompanies the book (Hennig, 2014b).

There are a growing number of works which seek to present social and economic data in a greater variety of visual forms, and data visualisation across many disciplines in the social sciences has taken hold. Geo-visualisations provide mechanisms to display representations of reality, based on spatial information (van den Brink et al., 2007), and the authors of this book have been at the forefront of some of these developments, presenting innovative forms of maps and cartograms for several years (see Dorling et al., 2010; Hennig, 2014a; Hennig et al., 2013). However, this book represents one of the first attempts to bring together visualisation of the human reality of the European population. *The Social Atlas of Europe* will be of wide interest not only to planners, geographers, other social scientists and policy makers, but also to members of the public across Europe (and beyond). One only needs to glance at the key areas that *Town Planning Review* lists as interests: spatial planning; local and regional economic development; community planning and participation social cohesion and spatial inequalities; urban design and conservation; environmental planning and sustainable development, to recognise why these maps provide stimulating material for discussion. The issues addressed in *The Social Atlas of Europe* lie at the heart of many issues which planners address on a daily basis, and the maps included present not only the diversity, but areas of commonality which may inform the work of planners. This book presents a

cartographic story of contemporary Europe, providing a new visual approach to the human geography of Europe, introducing the reader to a new way of viewing Europe.

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Explorations in Urban Design: an Urban Design Research Primer, Carmona M. (ed.), *Farnham, Ashgate, 2014, 398 pp., £30, ISBN: 978-1-4094-6266-8*

This extensive and well-illustrated volume provides a comprehensive overview of the field of urban design, bringing together contributions from 32 researchers at the Bartlett School at University College London, including the editor himself. Matthew Carmona has brought his considerable urban design knowledge to editing the collection, blending a diverse range of recent research into a coherent and engaging text which will offer readers many insights into the field. Additionally, as a research 'primer' it also offers something to inspire those wishing to engage in urban design research themselves by exploring the range of theoretical and methodological approaches that underpin this research. It will appeal to

a broad range of readers, from both within and beyond urban design, from postgraduate students embarking on dissertations and theses to established built environment scholars and practitioners. The research contributions are grouped according to their focus and approach into five sections; philosophical approaches, process investigations, physical explorations, propositional experiments and performance inquiry. The contributing chapters, five or six in each section, are concise and clearly written and structured, providing a useful reference source which can be 'dipped in and out of'. Care has been taken to avoid the overuse of obscure disciplinary 'languages' which might hinder rather than engage a multi-disciplinary audience and discussion of ideas is rigorous yet also accessible for those with differing backgrounds in built environment scholarship.

Carmona's postscript outlines the impetus for the book, which stemmed from

his concerns at the separation of urban design courses within the Bartlett School, operating in academic 'silos' which hindered the cross-fertilisation of ideas. This is an issue which not only besets urban design but is something that concerns urban research and management more broadly. This book therefore offers a welcome contribution to this wider project by providing both a flavour of the diversity of urban design as a discipline, and an attempt to highlight cross-cutting themes and ideas through Carmona's contextual chapter and his introductions to each section of the book. Carmona's introductory chapter provides an overview of the development and scope of urban design which will be of interest to both those familiar with, and those new, to the field. He considers debates around the identity of urban design and how the discipline connects to, and draws ideas from, fields of allied knowledge such as planning and architecture. However he contends that the diverse, 'mongrel' nature of urban design is healthy and important for crossing disciplinary boundaries in order to address the 'wicked' problems that stem from the complex messiness of contemporary cities. The issues and debates raised here will certainly resonate with those within other built environment disciplines, grappling with issues of disciplinary identity and focus.

The rest of the primer is designed to take the reader through particular meta-approaches to researching urban design in a deliberate attempt to try and cut across the limits of disciplinary classifications of research. In a further attempt to draw out wider themes, the research presented within each section is 'placed' in terms of three fundamental characteristics of research; primary/secondary evidence, subjective/objective inquiry and inductive/deductive approaches, and presented using a triangle graphic to illustrate its key characteristics.

This is quite a useful device linking the contributions together and emphasising their place within urban research more broadly. Having said this, readers might quibble with the placement of some chapters, although the editor acknowledges that the research presented frequently overlaps and often spans more than one section. This reflects the nature of much contemporary research that blends sources, methods and approaches and overall the logic of the grouping of contributions is clear.

The first section considers how urban design is engaging with a range of critical urban theories, including non-representational theory and post-colonial critiques. There is much here for others to consider how their research and practice engages with these wider ideas of the city as fluid, messy and diverse. Section two considers the process of design itself as an area for research, considering a diverse range of examples, including reviews of public space and street design projects to analysis of planning policy documents and the research challenges produced by the generation of data from 'smart cities'. Section three is concerned with explorations of the physical structure of cities and how this changes over time. Contributions are split between quantitative approaches using computing technology to understand and simulate urban development, drawing mainly on space syntax tools and approaches for which researchers at the Bartlett are well known, and historical, observational analysis grounded in traditions from urban morphological study. Section four presents a series of propositional experiments, which provide different 'takes' on design processes and projects. These are again wide ranging, considering both more traditional urban design practice through to more creative approaches applying writing, collage and story-telling to design practice. A

chapter considering design practice in cities in the Global South calls on urban design to 'de-colonise' and reconstruct in ways which can engage with the cultural differences in places where western design solutions have often been unproductively imposed. For planning scholars the final chapter in this section offers an interesting critical analysis of New Town design, employing a space syntax approach to assess the accessibility failings of their street layouts. The final section of the book, considering how places perform through use and time, is perhaps the most eclectic, including contributions employing anthropological investigation, stakeholder inquiry and historical analysis. Quentin Stevens' chapter highlights how

people's use of space is not always as intended by designers, which links usefully to the final chapter by Carmona which considers how to examine the success of urban design projects.

This book certainly opened my eyes to the breadth of urban design research being undertaken. It is well placed to fulfil its editor's ambitions to highlight the vibrancy of urban design as a discipline and contribute to the building of understanding across built environment disciplinary and professional divides which often constrain the examination of the complex problems associated with urban areas in the 21st Century.

HEATHER BARRETT [AQ1]

Transport, Climate Change and the City, Robin Hickman and David Banister, Abingdon, Routledge, 2014, 400 pp., £85.00, ISBN 978-0-415-66002-0

Cities are the heart of economic activity, social progress and human mobility. But this comes at the price of rising greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions that cities are both responsible for and exposed to. Unless something radically changes in the way we move within and between cities, we are set to make the Earth an unliveable place within a few generations. Concerns over the death toll of road accidents, the adverse health and well-being impacts of rapid motorisation, the consideration that energy resources are finite (even if somewhat weakened by recent reductions in energy demand and mobilisation of new conventional and unconventional energy sources) and – foremost and more than ever – the dangers of climate change have stirred ambitions and courage in a number of cities around the world leading to them taking bold

actions geared at sustainable travel. While the aspirations of city leaders, who have formed an *avant-garde* of decarbonisation, are now backed up by pledges of national governments the main question still remains; if and how can these aspirations be fulfilled.

Transport, Climate Change and the City provides insights into the state-of-the-art of urban travel, its effects on the environment, where it is heading, and what can be done to break the projected trends and achieve more sustainable travel behaviours. The book offers both a compelling account of how the urban world is slipping further into car dependency and an imaginative approach to thinking about and shaping future urban mobility. By taking a scenario approach to a very diverse set of cities – different in regards to size, demographics, urban form, geo-regional location, development opportunities and challenges, transport system characteristics and aspirations, and governance path dependencies – Hickman and Banister think about the impossible and how to make it possible.

For this purpose *Transport, Climate Change and the City* offers a matrix of four scenarios – (i) business as usual, (ii) clean but intense mobility, (iii) progressive travel with limited technological innovation and (iv) sustainable mobility – positioned on the axes of (x) technological innovation and (y) behavioural change. The shared conceptual framework is consistently used in the book to shape scenarios along transport policy priorities and available policy families – for urban structure, public transport, traffic demand management, low-emission vehicles, public realm and walking and cycling facilities, and ICTs – to encourage the implementation of future policy measures, and to quantify their potential impacts. This turns *Transport, Climate Change and the City* into an indispensable guidebook for policy-makers and practitioners, which explains a rationale for scenario building, steps to be taken, potential pitfalls, and outcomes to be expected in the sustainable future-making endeavour. At the same time, by supporting a statement that various transport policies across the world do matter in making sustainable and unsustainable mobility happen, this book issues both a promise and a warning to communities of practice.

What the interdisciplinary community of transport and mobility scholars will find in *Transport, Climate Change and the City* is a broader understanding of socio-technical change that moves beyond forecasting and capitalising on the impacts of technological innovation alone. By offering methodologies capable of quantifying carbon impacts of social change the book explores how affective and instrumental factors of behavioural change are equally important in designing sustainable mobility as technological innovation and advanced infrastructures provision. Hickman and Banister also point to broader sustainability impacts of the decarbonisation

agenda. This involves, in particular, the potential of using multi-criteria analysis in combination with participatory scenario-building to explore synergies between low carbon mobility on the one hand; and broader economic, social and environmental sustainability, on the other.

While *Transport, Climate Change and the City* signals some synergic effects of low carbon mobility policies, it is less explicit on tensions that they might bring about. I would have welcomed a more comprehensive discussion of the interplays between low carbon mobility, economic development and social justice. Some elements of a ‘conflict perspective’ would have strengthened the book. Urban communities from Bangkok to Los Angeles, not without reason, mobilise against incremental public transport investments. For example, a few of the tensions which arise from sustainable mobility are: mass transit systems, and sometimes also BRT, [AQ1], are unaffordable for large swathes of urban population; their development is likely to divert funding from existing public transport networks; severe parking issues arise around underground and BRT terminus stations; in some cases, such as the Bask [AQ2] Country HSR or the Turin TGV route, adverse local environmental impacts of HSR outweigh decarbonisation gains; and new underground lines tend to produce orbit situations where neighbourhoods well serviced by public transport are transformed into empty blown egg-shells while their old residents, forced out to remote locations, fall into car dependency. Furthermore, not only technologically advanced infrastructures but also walkable environments may reinforce gentrification processes; transformation of roads into cycling environments might have adverse impacts on local businesses; and the fight with urban sprawl through dense urban form correlates with undersupply of housing

and delivery of units that are of poor quality and small in size. While making sustainable mobility happen will inevitably involve wide-ranging costs, the question remains of how to secure legitimisation and fairness of their distribution. When coupled with local insights into who opposes sustainable transport solutions, on what grounds, and how they may be convinced to change their mind, the participatory scenario approach could greatly help in negotiating conflictive positions.

Transport, Climate Change and the City is stimulating and agonising. Just as any endeavour with such a great ambition, it may attract voices of readers who would have

wished more of something, but this in itself makes the book stir ambitions and creativity for imagining, designing and implementing more sustainable futures. This imaginative, well-evidenced and fantastically illustrated book is a must read for academics, students, transport professionals and local authority officers who embark on making our cities more sustainable and liveable places to live, work and play.

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